
An Improved GM(1,1) Model Based on Markov Correction and Its Application in Urban Acoustic Environments in China

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Abstract: To accurately predict the trend of urban environmental noise pollution in China, this paper, based on the grey GM(1,1) model, uses the Markov residual correction method to correct the grey prediction values and constructs an improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction. This model is applied to the regional acoustic environment of Jinan City, China, for instance verification and prediction analysis to demonstrate the effectiveness of the optimization strategy. The results show that the prediction accuracy and fitting effect of the improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction are significantly higher than those of the traditional GM(1,1) model. It has high accuracy in urban acoustic environment prediction and can meet the requirements of urban acoustic environment prediction in China.

Keywords: Urban sound environment; Grey prediction model; Residual correction; Markov process; Prediction accuracy

1. Introduction

In recent years, with the continuous advancement of urbanization, urban noise pollution has shown dynamic and complex characteristics, becoming a prominent environmental issue that affects the physical and mental health of residents, the quality of their living environment, and the sustainable development capacity of cities. The "China Noise Pollution Prevention and Control Report (2025)" released by the Ministry of Ecology and Environment of China [1] shows that in 2024, the total number of noise complaint cases across the country was approximately 5.895 million, an increase of 189,000 cases compared to the previous year. Moreover, noise disturbance issues accounted for 59.2% of all environmental pollution complaints and reports, ranking first among all environmental pollution factors. Currently, urban noise problems have become a key concern in China. Scientifically predicting the future development trend of urban acoustic environment quality can provide an effective mathematical method for urban acoustic environment quality prediction.

The urban sound environment is influenced by a variety of factors such as municipal public facility maintenance expenditure, urban population density, and vehicle flow, which interact with each other [2]. The monitoring results show strong random fluctuations and discrete sample characteristics, making the conventional prediction models insufficient in adaptability and stability, and unable to meet the prediction requirements of the sound environment in complex urban systems. The grey prediction model is a common prediction method that studies the entire uncertain system by processing limited sample data. It can achieve relatively reliable trend predictions under conditions of small sample sizes and poor information, and generally only four data points are needed to start the prediction [3]. Its basic principle is to transform the discrete time series into a more regular ordered generated sequence through appropriate processing of the original data. The differential equation established in this process is the grey model, with the most typical being the GM(1,1) model. In recent years, many scholars in China have deeply explored the applicability of this model in environmental prediction. Su Jing et al. [4] constructed a grey GM(1,1) model based on existing monitoring data to predict the development trends of environmental air, surface water, nearshore sea areas, and sound environment quality in Dalian during the "14th

Five-Year Plan" period. Bai Ling et al. [5] constructed a grey prediction model GM(1,1) to predict and analyze the development trend of the sound environment quality in Jiyuan City. However, the traditional GM(1,1) model is only suitable for sequence data with strong exponential laws and has poor processing capabilities for fluctuating data sequences, which will to some extent affect the prediction accuracy [6]. To solve this problem, some scholars have optimized the traditional grey model by using residual correction. Zhang Bingcai [7] constructed a residual correction GM(1,1) prediction model to predict and analyze the air quality in Yinchuan City. Li Zhen et al. [8] used a logarithmic curve to fit and correct the prediction results, constructed a residual correction GM(1,1) grey dynamic model group, and applied it to the actual urban water consumption data in Jining City for prediction and analysis. However, these correction models are generally based on the historical residual sequence for fitting, but they cannot determine the positive or negative attributes of the future residual correction, which limits the prediction results [9].

In response to the above issues, this paper integrates the advantages of the grey prediction model and the residual correction method in the modeling process, and introduces the Markov process to determine the sign of the residual prediction value, thereby constructing an improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction. This model is applied to the urban regional acoustic environment of Jinan City, China, for instance verification and prediction analysis. The prediction results prove that the prediction accuracy of the improved GM(1,1) model is significantly better than that of the traditional GM(1,1) model. It has high accuracy in short-term prediction of the urban acoustic environment in China and can provide a more scientific and effective modeling method for the prediction of the urban acoustic environment in China.

2. Development of the Grey Prediction Model

The traditional GM(1,1) model

Establish the original time series $x^{(0)}$ in chronological order, that is: $x^{(0)}=\{x^{(0)}(1),x^{(0)}(2),x^{(0)}(3),\dots,x^{(0)}(n)\}$; by accumulating $x^{(0)}$, a new time series $x^{(1)}$ can be generated: $x^{(1)}=\{x^{(1)}(1),x^{(1)}(2),x^{(1)}(3),\dots,x^{(1)}(n)\}$, where

$$x^{(1)}(k)=\sum_{i=1}^k x^{(0)}(i), k=1,2,3,\dots,n \quad (1)$$

Then the immediately adjacent mean sequence generated by $x^{(1)}$ is

$$z^{(1)}(k)=0.5[x^{(1)}(k)+x^{(1)}(k-1)], k=2,3,\dots,n \quad (2)$$

The first-order differential equation corresponding to the GM(1,1) model is

$$\frac{dx^{(1)}}{dt}+ax^{(1)}=b \quad (3)$$

In the formula, a represents the development coefficient, and b represents the grey action quantity.

It is transformed into the accumulation matrix B and the constant term vector Y :

$$B=\begin{bmatrix} -z^{(1)}(2) & 1 \\ -z^{(1)}(3) & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ -z^{(1)}(n) & 1 \end{bmatrix}, Y=[x^{(0)}(2),x^{(0)}(3),\dots,x^{(0)}(n)]^T \quad (4)$$

Let u be the parameter vector: $u=[a,b]^T$. Using the least squares method to solve for the parameters, we obtain

$$u=(B^T B)^{-1} B^T Y \quad (5)$$

After obtaining the value of u , the values of a and b can be determined. Substituting them into the above differential equation, the solution of the equation is found to be

$$x^{(1)}(k+1)=\left[x^{(0)}(1)-\frac{b}{a}\right]e^{-ak}+\frac{b}{a}, k=0,1,2,\dots,n-1 \quad (6)$$

The original predicted value can be obtained through decreasing and restoring:

$$x^{(0)}(k+1)=x^{(1)}(k+1)-x^{(1)}(k) \quad (7)$$

GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction

To enhance the prediction accuracy of the model, residual correction is required for the model. To prevent the influence of the positive and negative jumps in the residual sequence's sign, the residual sequence is normalized based on the residual calculation formula $\varepsilon^{(0)}(k) = x^{(0)}(k) - x^{(0)}(k)$, creating a new time series $\varepsilon_+^{(0)} = |\varepsilon^{(0)}(k)|$. The modeling steps of the residual GM(1,1) model are roughly the same as those of the traditional GM(1,1) model. A GM(1,1) model is established with $\varepsilon_+^{(0)}$ as the time series, and the time response function obtained is

$$\varepsilon_+^{(1)}(k+1) = \left[\varepsilon_+^{(0)}(1) - \frac{b_\varepsilon}{a_\varepsilon} \right] e^{-a_\varepsilon k} + \frac{b_\varepsilon}{a_\varepsilon}, k=0, \dots, n-1 \quad (8)$$

The fitted value of $\varepsilon_+^{(0)}$ can be obtained through one cumulative subtraction, that is

$$\varepsilon_+^{(0)}(k+1) = \varepsilon_+^{(1)}(k+1) - \varepsilon_+^{(1)}(k) \quad (9)$$

By applying the correction factor to restore the positive and negative signs of the corrected residuals, we obtain

$$\varepsilon^{(0)}(k) = u(k) \varepsilon_+^{(0)}(k) \quad (10)$$

In the formula, $u(k)$ represents the correction factor and satisfies $u(k) = \begin{cases} 1, \varepsilon^{(0)}(k) \geq 0 \\ -1, \varepsilon^{(0)}(k) < 0 \end{cases} k \geq 1$.

When $k > n$, the value of $u(k)$ is uncertain, and the sign attribute of $\varepsilon^{(0)}$ cannot be determined. Therefore, the Markov process can be used for estimation. The specific modeling steps are as follows:

- (1) For $k=1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, define the state E based on the sign of the residual $\varepsilon^{(0)}$. State E_1 indicates a positive residual ($\varepsilon^{(0)}(k) \geq 0$); state E_2 indicates a negative residual ($\varepsilon^{(0)}(k) < 0$).
- (2) Then calculate the state transition matrix:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} P_{11} & P_{12} \\ P_{21} & P_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

In the formula, $P_{i,j}$ represents the probability of the number of times the transition from state i to state j occurs, satisfying $P_{i,j} = \frac{m_{i,j}}{m_i}$. $m_{i,j}$ indicates the number of times the transition from state i to state j occurs, and m_i represents the total number of occurrences of state i .

- (3) Select the state of the last value of the residual sequence as the initial state vector u_0 . Let $u_0 = [u_1, u_2]$, where u_1 and u_2 respectively represent the probabilities of being in state 1 and state 2. That is, if the last residual value is positive, $u_0 = [1, 0]$; if it is negative, $u_0 = [0, 1]$. The state probability after t state transitions is obtained by $u_t = u_0 P^t$.

(4) In Equation (10), when $1 \leq k \leq n$, the sign of $u(k)$ corresponds to the sign of the corresponding value in the residual sequence $\varepsilon^{(0)}(k)$; When $k > n$, the state with the maximum probability after the transfer is used as the criterion for determining the sign attribute of the residual prediction value. If the probabilities of the two states are equal, the result of the previous calculation is taken.

- (5) By using $\varepsilon^{(0)}$ to correct for $x^{(0)}$, we obtain the residual-corrected GM(1,1) model:

$$x^{(0)}(k) = x^{(0)}(k) + \varepsilon^{(0)}(k) \quad (12)$$

The verification of model accuracy

This paper adopts the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) as the verification indicators for the accuracy of the prediction model [21]. The smaller the indicator values are, the higher the prediction accuracy of the model. The calculation formulas are as follows:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n |\varepsilon^{(0)}(k)| \quad (13)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \left| \frac{\varepsilon^{(0)}(k)}{x^{(0)}(k)} \right| \times 100\% \quad (14)$$

3. Case Verification

This paper applies the constructed prediction model to conduct relevant prediction analysis in the regional acoustic environment of Jinan City, China. The original data used are sourced from the publicly released noise monitoring data in the "China Statistical Yearbook". This paper selects a time scale from 2011 to 2024, totaling 14 periods of data. The sample size is small and the information is scarce, which meets the requirements of grey modeling. To verify the scientific nature of the optimization strategy, both the traditional GM(1,1) model and the improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction are applied to simulate and predict the regional environmental noise in Jinan City, and the results are compared with the original data.

The annual regional environmental noise monitoring data of Jinan City from 2011 to 2024 are as follows: 53.8, 52.3, 52.6, 54.2, 53.6, 53.1, 53.7, 53.3, 54.9, 55.1, 54.9, 55.0, 55.5, 55.0. The first 11 periods of data are the training set, used to build the prediction model for fitting and extrapolation prediction; the last 3 periods of sequence are the prediction set, used to verify the prediction performance of the prediction model.

(1) Firstly, the traditional GM(1,1) model was applied to simulate and predict the data of the first 11 periods, and

the prediction model was obtained as $x^{(0)}(k) = 10543.38345e^{0.004974085(k-1)} - 10489.58345$. The simulation values were 53.8, 52.6, 52.8, 53.1, 53.4, 53.6, 53.9, 54.2, 54.4, 54.7; the predicted values were 55.0, 55.5, 55.8.

(2) By subtracting the actual values from the predicted values, the residual sequence can be obtained as 0.0000, -0.2743, -0.2365, 1.1000, 0.2353, -0.5308, -0.1983, -0.8670, 0.4629, 0.3914, -0.0814, -0.2556, -0.0311, -0.8080. The first 11 residual data points were selected, normalized, and then subjected to grey modeling to obtain the

residual prediction model $\varepsilon_+^{(0)}(k) = -19.9081171e^{-0.024867034(k-1)} + 19.9081171$, with the simulated residual values being 0.0000, 0.4890, 0.4769, 0.4652, 0.4538, 0.4427, 0.4318, 0.4212, 0.4108, 0.4007, 0.3909; and the predicted residual values being 0.3813, 0.3719, 0.3628. The sign of the predicted residual values for the first 11 periods was corrected based on the original residual sequence.

(3) The Markov state transition probability matrix is obtained from the residual sequence as $P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.6 \\ 0.4 & 0.6 \end{bmatrix}$.

Taking the residuals from the 11th period as the initial state variable, the probabilities after the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd state transitions are calculated sequentially. It is found that the sign attributes of the subsequent three periods are all positive; these are then applied to the residual forecasts for the subsequent three periods to perform sign correction. Based on $x^{(0)}(k) = x^{(0)}(k) + \varepsilon^{(0)}(k)$, we can then obtain the forecast values from the Markov-corrected Grey GM(1, 1) model.

Table 1 presents the true values of the equivalent sound level of regional environmental noise in Jinan City, as well as the simulated and predicted values from the traditional and improved GM(1,1) models. Table 2 shows the model accuracy verification results of the traditional and improved GM(1,1) models.

Table 1: The true values of the equivalent sound level of regional environmental noise in Jinan City, the simulated values and predicted values of the traditional and improved GM(1,1) models

Data type	Year	True value	Traditional GM(1,1)		Improved GM(1,1) based on Markov correction	
			Predicted value	Relative error (%)	Predicted value	Relative error (%)
Training set	2011	53.8	53.8	0.00%	53.8	0.00%
	2012	52.3	52.6	0.52%	52.1	0.41%
	2013	52.6	52.8	0.45%	52.4	0.46%
	2014	54.2	53.1	2.03%	53.6	1.17%
	2015	53.6	53.4	0.44%	53.8	0.41%
	2016	53.1	53.6	1.00%	53.2	0.17%
	2017	53.7	53.9	0.37%	53.5	0.43%
	2018	53.3	54.2	1.63%	53.7	0.84%
	2019	54.9	54.4	0.84%	54.8	0.09%

Prediction set	2020	55.1	54.7	0.71%	55.1	0.02%
	2021	54.9	55.0	0.15%	54.6	0.56%
	2022	55.0	55.3	0.46%	54.9	0.23%
	2023	55.5	55.5	0.06%	55.2	0.61%
	2024	55.0	55.8	1.47%	55.4	0.81%

Table 2: The prediction accuracy test results of the traditional and improved GM(1,1) model

Data type	Model	MAE	MAPE
Training set	Traditional GM(1,1)	0.40	0.74%
	Improved GM(1,1) based on Markov correction	0.22	0.41%
Prediction set	Traditional GM(1,1)	0.36	0.66%
	Improved GM(1,1) based on Markov correction	0.30	0.55%

Figure 1 shows the comparison between the actual values of regional environmental noise in Jinan City and the prediction results of the traditional and improved GM(1,1) models. Figure 2 presents the comparison of the relative error results of the traditional and improved GM(1,1) models.

Figure 1: Comparison chart of the true value of regional environmental noise in Jinan City and the prediction results of traditional and improved GM(1,1) models

Figure 1: A comparison chart of the relative error results of the traditional and improved GM(1,1) models.

Combining Table 1, Table 2, Figure 1 and Figure 2, the fitting and prediction accuracy of the improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction is significantly higher than that of the GM(1,1) model, and it can effectively obtain the detailed information of the measured curve. Then, the error index values of MAE and MAPE are calculated, as shown in Table 2. Compared with the traditional GM(1,1) model, the MAE of the improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction in the training set fitting decreases from 0.40 to 0.22, and the MAPE decreases from 0.74% to 0.41%. In the prediction set prediction, the MAE decreases from 0.36 to 0.30, and the MAPE decreases from 0.66% to 0.55%. By comparing MAE and MAPE, it can be known that the prediction accuracy of the improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction is significantly better than that of the traditional GM(1,1) model, and it can better fit and predict the urban acoustic environment quality in China, verifying the effectiveness of the model optimization strategy.

4. Conclusion

This paper adopts the Markov residual correction method to modify the GM(1,1) model, constructs an improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction, and applies it to the fitting and prediction of the annual urban regional environmental noise sequence data in Jinan City, China, to verify the feasibility of the model. The following conclusions are drawn:

- (1) For the annual urban regional environmental noise sequence data with large random fluctuations, compared with the traditional GM(1,1) model, the improved GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction has a higher fitting effect and prediction performance, and the model simulation and prediction error index values are significantly reduced. It performs better in short-term prediction. Therefore, in the future, by relying on the prediction output of this model, it is possible to achieve a forward-looking prediction of the changing trend of urban regional noise, issue early warnings in a timely manner, identify over-standard risks, and provide data support for optimizing noise pollution prevention and control strategies and conducting refined management.
- (2) The improved grey GM(1,1) model based on Markov correction can mine the fluctuation information in the sequence by dividing states, which makes up for the limitations of the general residual correction GM(1,1) model in sequence prediction and improves the prediction accuracy of the sequence data.

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